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BB-2208 HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

**Case Study Analysis: Hazeeyah Agro Farm –
The Standard Causal Model of HRM**

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ABSTRACT

The central purpose of this paper is to examine the extent to which the enactment of HR practices can be seen as a factor which need to be taken into account in the standard casual of human resource management if an adequate explanation of the people management links to the organizational performance is to be made specifically in one of the local small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Brunei from the agro-based industry. Hazeeyah Agro Farm which based in Kampong Batang Duri, Temburong District is the chosen SME for this research and will further be discussed in this paper on how the company manage their human resource. Both primary and secondary research were used and data were collected from the published book and an interview with the owners of Hazeeyah Agro Farm. The standard causal model of HRM is the best approach for Hazeeyah Agro Farm to manage their business and the involvement with local agencies that provides entrepreneurial classes or programs could help Hazeeyah Agro Farm to sustain its business in the competitive agro market.

INTRODUCTION

The global and competitive market environment has led to new challenges. Businesses can lose the opportunity to compete with national and international competitors without having a well-trained and well-prepared labor force which can result in reduced economic success (Tomaka, 2001). Pfeffer and Jeffrey (1998) classified that the significance of 'selective recruiting' and highlighted that a deliberate method of recruitment and selection will ensure a better balance between organizational objectives and the skills and abilities of employees.

COMPANY BACKGROUND

Hazeeyah Agro Farm is a small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) based in Brunei who specialized in duck farm producing salted eggs situated in Temburong district. Hazeeyah Agro Farm is managed by a couple namely Nur Haziyah Abdul Rahman and Muhd Hazim Abdul Rahim Mangkiling. Hazeeyah Agro Farm started their business in 2015 with just 12 ducks in the farm and currently they only have 4 employees including themselves and it is a family-oriented business. Initially, Nur Haziyah and Muhd Hazim still uncertain about the market and unsure how to rear ducks. As per interview with the owners, they stated that the farm is currently about 0.7 acres and just enough to fit in all the ducks. The couple have bought a batch of 450 ducks which is also the standard quantum for what their farm and number of ducks can accommodate which also to ensure the well-being of the ducks and able to produce high quality eggs for the consumers. Practically, Hazeeyah Agro Farm can produce about 400-500 eggs per day and currently they have an estimate number of 800 ducks. As mentioned by the couple, a batch of 300 ducks does not mean they can expect to get 300 eggs but instead it can be less in numbers of production. The eggs will be collected every day and needed to be cleaned. The overall process of producing the eggs includes breeding, cleaning and soaking the eggs in the salt water.

METHODOLOGY

1. Published book (secondary research)

A published book entitled “Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei” was provided where number of local agripreneurs were featured in it and Hazeeyah Agro Farm was one of the featured lists. The book was provided as a support and reassurance for the company case study analysis.

The book also provide thorough overview of the chosen company and valuable source that can be used for the case analysis. Although there is no much information regarding human resource management for Hazeeyah Agro Farm, a deeper information was needed for the case analysis. Thus, an informal interview with the owners was conducted.

2. Interview (primary research)

An informal interview was carried out with Hazeeyah Agro Farm team during the visit on 24th October, 2020. During the interview, the owners were willing to express their experiences and concerns in regards with the workplace, which enabled myself to discover what needed to be improved on and at the same time exchanging ideas and opinions with them especially on their human resource management.

The Interview was very useful to discover the owner’s perceptions and beliefs regarding the work environment and ethics implemented. In comparison with other evaluation methods platforms, face-to-face interview offers in-depth comprehension through interpersonal connection made during the interview especially for feedback evaluations. Moreover, the instant reaction through the interview provide a more honest and real time response which can eliminate an act of nepotism or dishonest answers which always happen to other feedback evaluation platforms. Hence, the interview does help in increasing the accuracy of the evaluation.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

It is important to accept two different opinions from one point of view stating that HRM is just a viewpoint on personnel management and high concept personnel management while it is also highlighted that the innovative essence of HRM is through emphasizing the value of strategic alignment, high participation, high flexibility and quality (Guest,1987). There are few problems faced by Nur Haziyah and Muhd Hazim in managing their business focusing on their human resource management as such:-

1. Nur Haziyah and Muhd Hazim did not have any qualifications higher than secondary education. The couple did not have any much knowledge in operating such big business which includes ability to breed the ducks suitably which then restraining them from handling the right employees for their company.
2. Hazeeyah Agro Farm has only four employees which includes the couple themselves and two of their children. As per interview with the owners, they only focusing on their current employees and have no plan to expand their number of employees at the meantime. In addition, the owners mentioned that they also get seasonal employees which is not permanent workers and will only hire them when needed especially during peak seasons on the hatchability of the duck eggs.
3. In relation to the problem point number two, as per interview with the Hazeeyah Agro Farm's owners, they stated that they are planning to expand their duck farms to a larger scale and did not mentioned to actually recruit more employees to work under them.

CASE ANALYSIS

The approach of using The Standard Causal of Human Resource Management

Prowse & Prowse (2010) stated that there has been an increased interest in HRM over the last 30 years. Hazeeyah Agro Farm needs to strategize its management specifically on their employee's management in order to sustain their business. Strategize their management here means to use a strategy that followed by an organization which includes a portfolio of interests used to measure the success of the organization by the organization to acquire or maintain, along with the financial ratio such as return on investment, return on sale and return on capital employed. Hazeeyah Agro Farm need to recruit proper number of employees to work with them in order to sustain it as the market of breeding duck eggs in Brunei is really encouraging. Intan (2008) mentioned that salted egg trend in Brunei has hit boiling point which even after 12 years now Bruneian are still fanatics with the salted eggs.

Organizational strategy can be defined as an attempt of an organization to find ways in positioning their business's objectives to maximize the use of their human capital. This can be applied to Hazeeyah Agro Farm company as it is important for them to maximize the usage of their human assets in order to achieve their company's objectives and competitive advantage. Such human resource practice that can be used for Hazeeyah Agro Farm is the standard causal of HRM. The standard causal model of HRM is one of the most best-known HR practices. The standard causal model of HRM is derived from several comparable versions that were released in the 90s and early 2000s. The model displays a causal chain that begins with the business strategy and ends with improved financial results through the HR processes (see Table 1).

Table 1 – The Standard Causal Model of HRM

Hazeeyah Agro Farm firstly need to revise its organizational objectives which then lead to proper company strategy in order to improve their business performance through HR activities. The standard causal of HRM shows how HR activities and practices can be more effective if it is aligned with the company’s strategy and thus, the proper HR strategy derived from the overall strategy.

The standard causal model of HRM illustrates an underlying chain that starts with the business plan and with fiscal output. According to this method, human resources are only useful if their approach represents the company’s plan which is the best-fit hypothesis. Additionally, social resource plans are accompanied by HR practices that includes proper hiring, appropriate employee’s training, employees rewards, better appraisal and compensating the employees. Hence, these HR practices will lead to certain outcomes such as better employee’s commitment, employee’s engagement and overall quality output performance for Hazeeyah Agro Farm. Such HRM outcomes will contribute to internal output in turn for Hazeeyah Agro Farm which includes better productivity, enhance creativity, and efficiency. These results may also consists of financial turnover, better margins, better return of investment that contribute to overall Hazeeyah Agro Farm financial’s success.

There are two interesting relationship underlying in the standard causal of HRM chain which are the unmediated HRM effect and the reverse causality. The unmediated HRM effects shows some HR practices that can directly lead to improved Hazeeyah Agro Farm's internal efficiency such as an effective employee's training that can directly results in improved performance without inherently impacting the HR outcomes. Moreover, the reversed causality in the model chain shows that higher financial performance often leads to more investment in HR activities and better HR outcomes as employees are also more engaged when output is strong. The reversed causality in this approach often shows better performance results in higher investments in the customs of human resource to improve HR outcomes (DeCenzo et al., 2016).

ALTERNATIVE SOLUTIONS

It is important for Hazeeyah Agro Farm to have an effective management of human resource for their business using the standard causal model of HRM as part of their employee's engagement in the company. They key functions of using the approach include recruiting new employees, giving proper training for the new employees, using performance appraisals as part of the employee's retention, motivate the employees by giving suitable compensations as well as good workplace communication between employers and employees.

In addition, having a recruitment is one of the major responsibility for Hazeeyah Agro Farm to initiate, in order to retain their employees. Haazeyah Agro Farm need to hire suitable HR managers for their company to hire the right kind of people to work with them. The HR managers will then be responsible to come up with a plans and strategies on recruiting and training for their employees. Moreover, it will be beneficial for Hazeeyah Agro Farm to develop public relations in order to build up relationships with other business sectors and plays an active role in managing the business marketing plans.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Due to the rapid competition and environmental change towards providing more innovative services and other business challenges, the disciplines and ideas cannot be fixed. In human resource management, it is important to consider workers as assets and not expenses. There is no consensus in scientific literature as to what serve as a source of competitive advantage as some authors stated that sustained competitive advantage lies in human resources, other authors maintain that competitive advantage is created by HRM practices and not human resources.

Engaged employees contribute to a better performance. Therefore, the interactions in using the standard causal model of HRM approach are not always unidirectional. In general, the standard causal model of HRM explains how a human resource strategy is structured and the implications of human resources on the organizational process and the organization's financial performance for Hazeeyah Agro Farm.

Hazeeyah Agro Farm would also need to maintain its relationships and involvement with LiveWIRE and DARE in order to increase their knowledge in the business field and able to run and sustain their business in a long term. By involving with such entrepreneurial programs provided by LiveWIRE and DARE will help Hazeeyah Agro Farm to analyze any issues related to their capabilities and knowledge towards local entrepreneurial environment.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Human resource management should have attracted such attention from the owners of Hazeeyah Agro Farm. From the strategic viewpoint, Lengnick-Hall and Lengnick-Hall (1988) analyze a visible rationale for endorsing the HRM approach; 1) For complex organizational challenges, HRM provides a wider variety of solutions; 2) HRM allows the individuals who execute and comprise the strategy and; 3) It guarantees that when objectives are set or capabilities evaluated, the people of the organization are considered as well as its technological and financial resources.

It is crucial for Hazeeyah Agro Farm to have an effective management of human resource for their business. By having an effective management of human resource, it will help to bridge the gaps between Hazeeyah Agro Farm's employees and the company's strategic objectives. The role of human resource management in Hazeeyah Agro Farm is enormous, from recruiting and training of the current or future employees to the management of conflicts and all financial responsibilities in the company ensuring a healthy work-life balance. Management of human resources will not only help to keep their employees satisfied and well educated, it also ensures that Hazeeyah Agro Farm operates within the legal requirements and addresses any liability concerns that may occur. Furthermore, having a proper management of employees will help to build the organizational culture and environment in which the employees have the competency, commitment and interest to serve their customers well for a better business sustainability.

Appendix

Photos of our site visit to Hazeeyah Agro Farm, Kampong Batang Duri, Temburong and an interview session with the owners.

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